

IMPROVING ARGUMENTATION ABOUT THE OEDIPUS COMPLEX

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ABSTRACT

This article addresses the Oedipus Complex and its relationship with the development of children and their personality towards the formation of the adult personological structure, through adolescence. Its scientific relevance lies in the possibility of expanding the debate, discussions and arguments about this event that spans human existence in two distinct moments, childhood and adolescence, contributing to the healthy formation of the human Ego and Superego. Its social relevance lies in the fact that it allows the broad public to discuss and study the subject with deference and knowledge. This is a bibliographical research, based on classic authors who dedicated themselves to the study and academic-scientific production of the topic. The Oedipus Complex is a discovery of Psychoanalysis, based on Sigmund Freud's investigations with his neurotic patients and, mainly, through a complex, deep and painful self-analysis. It is structured around Sophocles' tragedy, in which his character, Oedipus, kills his father and marries his mother without knowing it. In search of the truth about himself, he discovers he is a parricide and an incestuous man. Even if it is intended to place all the blame on his shoulders, he acted without knowing that he committed such violations. Sigmund, throughout his scientific life, presented several hypotheses and theories that could, in some way, clarify the occurrence of the Oedipus Complex phenomenon. He believed that man evolved from a specimen that reached adulthood at five years of age and, as the complex occurs around three and a half years of age, this could mean gonadotropic maturation, culminating in the genetic cathexial discharge ring. He continues to argue that in the evolutionary process, man gained survival, with his existence extended ad infinitum, in what can be interpreted by the unconscious, arriving at the current model of psychosexual development.

Keywords: Oedipus Complex. Sigmund Freud. Ego Development. Greek tragedy.

INTRODUCTION

Psychoanalysis, through its discoveries about the unconscious and its mechanisms, has made extremely important contributions to contemporary society and to many of the sciences that have developed from the need to explain human behavior in society; moreover, in the midst of a coexistence that has become strange, complex and destructive. The discoveries of brain mechanisms and their functioning, and moreover, the developmental phases, represent a milestone in the history of humanity. Sigmund Freud did not create anything extremely new;

however, he brought to the circle of academic discussions problems that until then had been ignored and considered irrelevant or treated through the prism of religion or charlatanism. One of these phenomenal contributions discovered was the *Oedipus Complex*, which is a triangular conflict that occurs within the family, becoming the elementary basis for the consolidation of the adult human personality.

Freud explains that the struggle between libido and ego begins in early childhood. The first pleasure of a newborn child is that of suckling, and Freud considers this pleasure to be sexual. From the cradle, a child loves its mother; however, society acts in such a way that sexual interest is neither expressed nor accepted as such. It is true that the pleasure that a child feels for its mother does not occur without obstacles. On the one hand, the father has a right to the mother and in this respect is the child's rival. The result is the Oedipus complex: the child loves its mother and hates its father. It is true that the child can also love its father, and in this case its attitude is ambivalent – it loves and hates the same person.

The same complex, developed in a somewhat different way, also occurs with the girl: she loves her father and hates her mother or develops an ambivalent attitude towards her. This whole situation, with its violent loves and jealousies, with its inevitable conflicts and repressions, determines an enormous amount of effort and psychic tension, which can give rise to endless emotional disorders. However, it must be clarified that it is not the Oedipal conflict that causes disorders in individual life, reflected in social behavior; rather, it is the lack of awareness of it and the way in which it develops until its dissolution that will determine the construction of a healthy personality structure, especially with regard to sexuality.

The study of the Oedipus Complex is a process that requires the interpretation of clinical cases that arrive at clinics and the behavioral analysis of children who are going through this phase of psychic development. It has happened that most people interpret the phenomenon from a hasty reading of texts written without permission and which give examples of every situation of sexual conflict as a manifestation of the aforementioned complex, and this, apparently, clarifies the entire situation.

Understanding what happens in a child's head, leading him to such excessive actions of jealousy and longing for the disappearance of one of his spouses, which would allow him to possess the object of desire, is something that occurs in his unconscious world, outside of his conscious domain and that, when he realizes that the loss of one of his parents would affect him, he enters a state of conflict, generating feelings of guilt, which he carries throughout his existence, causing him to psychically distance himself from the loved object; because, in order

to possess it, he would have to pay a very high price, which is to lose the protection of someone who, in a strange way, also loves him.

The term Oedipus complex was given this name based on Freud's studies to find an answer to the problem of aggression observed in children between the ages of three and a half and five, when they clung to maternal protection and, in a strange way, rejected the male figure. The child's unconscious attitude, which here can refer to an act not thought through in a rationalized way, hides a fear of being deprived of the object of their love, namely the figure of the opposite sex. In Greek mythology, the character who lent his name to the aforementioned sexual conflict murders his father, without knowing what he was doing, and marries his own mother, also unaware of the plots of destiny, set up and prepared for him.

Sigmund is enchanted by the discovery of the Oedipus Complex and its possible connection with his studies, based on the tragic hero, because despite Oedipus having tried at all costs to escape his fateful destiny, predicted by an oracle as a curse upon him, he ends up carrying out his saga methodically. In the same way, modern, real man cannot escape his phylogenetic heritage, depending on it to become an adult, mature and sexually balanced.

THE OEDIPUS COMPLEX

The initial bond of every male or female child is established with the mother. For much of childhood, she is the central object of the bonds of comfort, pleasure and protection. If the mother was the effective, desired and pleasurable emotional support, she will be the closest woman to whom the boy will feel attracted. The attraction that the boy will feel for the mother, with sexual characteristics, will be a natural consequence of this process. And it is on the basis of this love and this natural attraction that, although later repressed, the basic model of male-female attraction is created. It is important to emphasize, however, that the attraction of the son to the mother leads to the organization of a triangle in which the father, possessor of the mother, representative of the law, prohibits the son's desires. The conflict gives rise to the fear of castration. The strength of this fear, quite severe for a normal child, leads him, at first, to identify defensively with the father, thus constructing his initial masculine organization. Since identification does not eliminate the conflict, he is led to repress his desire for the mother. This repression has two evolutionary consequences: firstly, it encourages sublimation and entry into the latency period; secondly, it crystallizes the constitution of the superego.

This set of psychic phenomena was designated by psychoanalytic theory as the Oedipus Complex. The unconscious conflict between son and father for possession of the mother and

for power has been the theme of great classical tragedies throughout history, such as *Oedipus the King* (a tragedy by Sophocles, written in the 5th century BC) and *Hamlet* (a tragedy by Shakespeare, written in the 16th century). Freud uses Sophocles' tragedy to call the triangular conflict established as the Oedipus Complex.

The plot portrayed in the play, and also in the myth on which it is based, is a deep terrain that can be explored *ad infinitum*, ranging from the most distant traditions of current culture to the apparently most trivial events that take over human phylogenetic and ontogenetic existence. Oedipus is not seeking revenge; he is seeking an elucidation of his life which, until the event in his city, provoked by an envious drunkard, could not have been calmer and more serene. He had been raised to be the tyrant of the city of Corinth, in place of his adoptive father, a condition of which he was completely unaware, as were almost all the people, with rare exceptions.

The entire plot that unfolds after this is Oedipus trying to escape his destiny; but no matter how hard he tried, he came closer to fulfilling it according to the natural order of things, since his father, Laius, by getting rid of him, left his condition vacant, upon his departure, without a legitimate successor. Perhaps this was the reason why the king of Thebes went to the Oracle, for a new consultation, in order to know if the curse cast upon him still persisted, since he depended on an heir to succeed him in command of the Polis.

The story of Oedipus begins with Laius, his biological father, still in the court of King Pelops and ends with the tragedy *The Seven Against Thebes*. Laius was king of Thebes and lived with Jocasta, who for many years had no children. In his eagerness to have an heir, he consulted the oracle of Apollo in Delphi and received the following answer: "Laius, you will have a son, but know that you are destined to die at the hands of your own son. This was determined by Zeus, the son of Cronus, who heeded the curse of Pelops, whose son you abducted."

As a young man, Laius had been expelled from his country and had gone to stay at the court of King Pelops, who took him in. While there, he kidnapped Chrysippus, the king's son. The young man, ashamed, committed suicide. It should be clarified, for educational purposes, that the expression kidnapping, in this context, means rape and not kidnapping, as it is associated with modern thought. Other sources report that Laius seduced his host's son, introducing him to homosexuality, and the boy, becoming the target of ridicule at court, committed suicide.

History tends to alleviate much of what is presented based on interpretations of the contemporary world and its way of understanding individual actions. Certainly, King Pelops, when confronted by his son about not wanting to marry and leave him heirs and even not being

able to take his father's place in command of the city, is given the option of assuming the role of a man of honor, marrying and perpetuating himself, as the law determined, or he would be forced to commit suicide, as the law itself determined.

Despite fearing the Oracle's warning, Jocasta gave her husband a son. Remembering the prophecy, and to prevent it from coming true, they had the child's feet pierced when he was three days old and abandoned, with his feet tied, on Mount Cithaeron. The shepherd responsible for this cruel crime took pity on the innocent child and gave him to another shepherd, who was tending the flocks of King Polybus of the city of Corinth.

The shepherd of Polybus untied the boy's pierced feet and named him Oedipus, which means "*the one with swollen feet*", because of his wounds, and took him to Corinth, to be with his master. King Polybus took pity on the boy and gave him to his wife Merope, who raised him as if he were her own son. However, a chance event threw Oedipus into the depths of despair. A Corinthian, who envied the young man's prominent position, got drunk on wine at a banquet, took Oedipus aside and told him that he was not a legitimate son of his parents. The young man decided to consult an oracle who, instead of giving him an answer, only revealed a much greater misfortune that hung over his head, whose fate was inevitable: "You will kill your own father, marry your mother and leave a shameful offspring."

Desperate at the revelation, he fled to Boeotia. At a crossroads, he met a carriage in which an unknown old man was riding, accompanied by a messenger, a driver and two servants. The driver pushed the pedestrian, who had found them in that narrow passage of the road. Oedipus struck the rude driver. The old man decided to avenge his servant and struck the stranger hard on the head with his spear. Beside himself, Oedipus raised his staff and knocked the old man from his seat, killing him.

He felt certain that he had taken revenge on some Phocaeen or Boeotian who had threatened his life, for the old man he had met bore no sign of his position. However, the murdered man was Laius, king of Thebes, his legitimate father. Soon after this event the Sphinx appeared before the gates of Thebes. She sat on a rock and from there she proposed all sorts of riddles to the inhabitants of the city. Anyone who did not know the solution was destroyed and devoured. This situation led the prince to decree that he would give the kingdom and his sister Jocasta as his wife to the one who could free the city from the terrible monster that frightened everyone.

Attracted by the adventure and the prize offered, Oedipus arrived in Thebes. He did not mind risking his life, because of the prophecies that were hanging over him. He went to the Sphinx and asked her to present him with a riddle. The monster wanted to propose an insoluble

enigma to the bold stranger and said the following: “In the morning it has four legs, at noon two and at dusk three. Of all creatures, it is the only one to change the number of legs, but precisely when this number is greater, the strength and speed of its limbs are less.”

Oedipus smiled as he heard the riddle, which did not seem so difficult to solve. “The answer to your riddle is the human being,” he said, “who, at the dawn of life, is a weak child, crawling on two arms and two legs. Then, in the middle of life, becomes strong and walks on two legs. Finally, in the evening of life, becomes an old man and, needing support, takes a cane to serve as a third leg.” The riddle was solved. Overcome with shame and despair, the Sphinx threw herself from the top of the rock, committing suicide. As a reward, Oedipus received the kingship of Thebes and the hand of the widow, who was his own mother. Thus, the prophecy was firmly on its way to fulfillment.

For a long time the terrible secret was hidden from everyone and Oedipus, a good and just king, although he had some defects, reigned happily over Thebes and was loved by the people, alongside Jocasta. Some time later the gods caused an epidemic to strike the city, killing many people, and for which no remedy could be found. An oracle had informed a servant of the city that Apollo had ordered a criminal who was sheltering there to be expelled from the city, and not to do anything that could not be redeemed by any punishment, since the murder of King Laius hung over the country like a heavy guilt. Oedipus, upset, sent two messengers to the blind seer, Tiresias, whose vision of the unknown was comparable to that of the god Apollo. The seer told him that he was the king's murderer and that he was living with his mother in a cursed relationship.

There was no doubt: the terrible event had been revealed. With a cry of madness, Oedipus hurriedly withdrew. He broke down the locked double doors of his mother's room and entered. A hideous sight appeared before his eyes. He saw Jocasta, with her hair in disarray, hanging from a rope, hanged, over her bed. Oedipus stood paralyzed for a long time, staring at the dead woman, and then he approached her groaning. He released the rope, let the corpse fall to the floor and tore off the golden clasps of the woman's dress. He lifted her with his right hand, cursed his own eyes, which had been forced to witness this, and pierced them with the buckle of his belt.

Oedipus handed over the throne to his brother-in-law so that he could reign in the name of his young sons, and asked for a tomb for his unfortunate mother. He placed his daughters under the protection of the new king and asked to be expelled from those lands. Struck by blindness, his fate was to wander through foreign lands, seeking asylum in the city of Colonus, which welcomed him and gave him a tomb in an unknown place.

For some time, the girl's love for her father was called *the Electra complex*, but nowadays, since the underlying principle is the same in both sexes, the term *Oedipus complex* is applied to both. The development of the Oedipus complex in the girl is more indirect and more complicated than in the boy. This is because the object of incestuous love is also an object of love of the same sex; therefore, it must carry out two object transfers in opposite directions, which demands a greater charge of energy and psychic balance.

In this game, the boy not only feels jealous of his mother towards his father, but also towards any other figure who may be threatening to the object of his love and emotional possession. In social situations where he sees his mother showing affection towards other individuals of the opposite sex, the child reacts by creating confusion, attacking or becoming more attached to his mother, demanding more attention from her; in some cases, he becomes aggressive and violent.

One thing that cannot be ignored without a preponderant understanding is that even if a child goes through the Oedipus Complex phase without expressing his/her conflict, this silence, on the other hand, does not mean that he/she has escaped the influence; only that, somehow, the confrontation that is expected, in all cases, has not been put out there, which does not allow us to defend the absurd idea that this aspect of peaceful occurrence means that he/she will have psychological problems in adulthood. On the contrary, those individuals who most exasperate their conflictual nuances during the Oedipus complex phase reveal a better chance of having an adult sexual life marked by conflicts of all kinds.

Defining the role of parents during this transition is an [*almost*] impossible task, because there is no way to predict how the complex will reveal itself or how the child will receive and respond to the conflict situation in which he or she will be emotionally involved. The parents' attitude should be as pedagogical as possible, leading the situation in such a way that the solution and dissolution of the Oedipus complex occurs autonomously, allowing the child to advance towards the latency phase, strictly speaking. For Gastão Pereira da Silva, "the Oedipus complex, whose description has made the hair stand on end and exalted the feeling of guilt of so many moralists, incapable of looking inside themselves, because they cannot resist the descent into the depths of their own soul. However, as Alice Balint says so well, the Oedipus complex is not a profession of faith, nor a dogma, nor a theory created to explain certain facts, but, __ quite the opposite __ the Oedipus complex is a description and a synthesis of occurrences that each one can observe" (PEREIRA DA SILVA, 1968, p. 143).

Oedipus is the son of the king of Thebes. When he was born, the Oracle revealed to his parents the terrible prophecy that he would kill his father and marry his mother. Fearful, his

parents, Laius and Jocasta, handed him over to a shepherd to be killed. By chance, another shepherd from a distant land took pity on the child and convinced the first to hand him over and tell the king that the task had been accomplished. Oedipus was then taken to Corinth, where the kings Polybus and Merope, who were sterile in marriage, adopted him. As an adult, Oedipus consulted the oracle and, upon learning of the prophecy, fled Corinth to avoid tragedy. Unaware of his adopted status, and therefore of his origin, he returned to Thebes. On the way, due to a disagreement that occurred on the road, he killed Laius, unaware that he was killing his own father. He solved the riddle proposed to him by the Sphinx that was ravaging the city of Thebes and destroying it. As a reward, he receives his mother, the widowed queen, marries her, has children, and thus the prophecy is fulfilled. The stage of the tragedy begins at this moment. The play begins when Oedipus tries to discover why the angry gods are ravaging Thebes with plagues. The course of the drama is the process of the King discovering the truth. Several relationships described by Sophocles are constitutive elements of the human structure, which are taken up by Freud in the theory of psychoanalysis. Oedipus is a decipherer of enigmas; however, he cannot, alone, decipher the enigma of his own life.

The time of Sophocles (5th century BC) represented a time of great scientific effervescence and in which the personal dramas and psychological conflicts inherent to man could be discussed with great breadth and depth. Ethics, vanity, love, passion, dreams, the darkest desires, all of these were subjects that were already being discussed outside the stages of tragic theater in select groups of thinkers. Myths were stories with a cautionary tone that were part of the existence of the Greeks, being taken as a point of interpretation and analysis of individual behavior.

Sophocles does not generalize; but reveals that the son's incestuous desire for his mother is part of the human condition, which is expressed latently in dreams. Socrates and Plato had already revealed and discussed something similar; they did not refer specifically to the maternal figure; however, they clarified that in dreams, human beings enjoy a freedom that surpasses all limits known and determined by reason. It was by taking these points, already superficially addressed by the Greeks of the Classical Era, that Sigmund sought to deepen the understanding of human behavior and what kept it under control, allowing it to manifest itself in events such as dreams or in art, and he tried to understand why, even appearing in such surreal situations, they aroused such horror in spectators.

The idea of a son's possessive desires towards his mother and the feelings of hostility towards his main rival in this battle made everyone's hair stand on end, and the ladies in Vienna blushed just at the mention of Freud's name. The scandal was not in what Sigmund had exposed;

rather, in the way he had done it, because unlike anthropologists who treated people from overseas as primitive wild beasts and practitioners of all sorts of bizarre attitudes, he took as his object of study the Viennese bourgeois family, the so-called and supposed civilized man. The most interesting thing is that it was from his studies and interpretation of the behavior of the man in a suit and tie and the ladies of high bourgeois society that anthropologists were able to make their comparisons, taking the opposite path to what had been advocated until then.

The anthropological discoveries achieved were splendid and, contrary to what is usually attempted to make us believe, they did not contradict the discoveries of the Master of Vienna. On the contrary, they corroborated and broadened the horizons of analysis, proving that the Oedipus Complex is a universal occurrence. Sigmund thus expresses himself about it: “You will undoubtedly wish to know once and for all what this terrible Oedipus complex consists of. The name suggests it. You are all certainly familiar with the Greek legend of King Oedipus who, having been condemned by fate to murder his father in order to marry his own mother, did everything he could to escape the oracle’s prediction. Unable to do so, he punished himself by gouging out his eyes when he realized that, without knowing it, he had committed both crimes, just as the divinity had predicted. (...) It is singular that Sophocles’ tragedy has not provoked the slightest indignation in the reader and that harmless psychoanalytic theories are the object of such exaggerated repulsion. Oedipus is, in essence, an abnormal work, because it suppresses man's responsibility, attributing to the power of divinity the initiative of crime and showing, on the other hand, that the individual's moral tendencies lack the strength to resist the impulses of crime. In the hands of a poet like Euripides, an enemy of the gods, the tragedy of Oedipus would have been a powerful weapon against divinity and against destiny. Sophocles, however, who is a believer, avoids this possible interpretation of his work, through a pious subtlety, proclaiming that the supreme morality demands obedience to the will of the gods, even when they order crime” (FREUD *apud* PEREIRA DA SILVA, 1968, p. 144).

Freud seeks to discuss the value of the original work, where even though the tragic hero is a criminal, in fact, for two heinous crimes, the weight of his actions does not have a dark impact on the work, making it a classic and not an instrument of aversion. He attributes this feeling to the poetic expertise of the playwright, who manages to direct all the blame for Oedipus's excessive actions to fate and the sovereign and insurmountable will of the gods, to whom men were responsible for the most insidious obedience. However, even with all the expressed nonconformity, Sigmund knows that this is how human beings behave, who are induced by love and unconscious desire to take possession of their object of love, defending it with violence and aggression. All this behavior cannot be controlled by internal reason,

requiring external sanctions on the individual to prevent them from exceeding the limits imposed by the Superego.

It turns out that Sigmund will take the Oedipus Complex as part of a process of formation of the human personality and identity; not as an aberration of nature and, perhaps [*just perhaps*], the tragedy of Oedipus the King did not awaken such a profound pathetic condition as he expected it to, because it was a situation placed there, at that specific stage, by *Physis itself*. It was not easy for him to reach such a conclusion, since he himself feels horrified by this idea taking up his time and his search for the truth about human personality development. However, he advances on the details that are presented to him through the clinic and develops a theory that manages to explain the phenomenon and its occurrence, without this seeming so devastating for human life and existence, highlighting the possibility of placing a cathexal burden of guilt on the individual that could represent a neurosis for his future psychological condition. His propositions clarify how extremely complex issues can be treated in an open and enlightening way without this leading to bizarre and unreasonable interpretations. From this understanding, many cases could be analyzed within Psychology and Forensic Psychiatry, exploring the ambiguous and confusing feelings that take over the child, still young, and that, if not handled carefully, culminate in outbursts of rage and aversive behavior, requiring specialized treatment.

Similar to the mythological character, the individual who finds himself stuck in the Oedipus phase lives running away from his responsibilities as a man and, every time he is challenged by life to assume them, he avoids them, hiding behind the most diverse reasons, precisely because each object of female love that he chooses for himself is a representation of his mother; therefore, unconsciously, he is committing a heinous and repulsive crime, which leads him to distance himself from his loves without further explanation. The serene dissolution of the Oedipus Complex is one of the most important stages of human existence, which Sigmund spent his entire life discussing and treating, since most of his patients presented neurotic symptoms due to some occurrence during this phase of psychic development, thus leaving their psychic economy compromised.

In the play, Freud feels enchanted because Oedipus, even though he is wise, cannot elucidate the great enigma that accompanies and pervades him. A blind man, literally, who does not see formal external reality, is the first to arrive at the truth. He realizes that Oedipus already has the elements to discover it, but does not want to, or rather, cannot do so. The process is analogous to that described by Freud, when the patient, upon discovering his truths, realizes that he has always known them; but, for some reason, he could not perceive them. When told

by the blind man that he had killed his father, Oedipus does not admit it. This resembles an early interpretation in Psychoanalysis, in which the “analysand” is still unable to face the truth. When the truth is finally discovered, a rigid Superego forces them to self-realization: Jocasta commits suicide and Oedipus, terrified by that vision, gouges out his own eyes.

This condition of being faced with the truth and not being able to confront it is a condition of a weakened ego, not necessarily an ego-dystonic one, and the unconscious itself takes care to provoke this gnosiological myopia, with the intention of preserving the individual's psychic health, perhaps even his life. Oedipus does not do as Jocasta did; he simply blinds himself because he had the curse of seeing, horrified, a scene that crosses his mind, that of his mother and wife swaying lifeless in her room.

Under a more blunt analysis, he was the only one responsible for all the misfortune that had befallen his family, simply because he tried to escape his fateful destiny. If he had questioned his own adoptive parents about that insult committed by a drunkard, they would have convinced him that it was the act of a fool, dominated by drink and envy. On the other hand, Laius, his biological father, went to consult the oracle under the stigma of fear of a curse that hung over his head; however, the idea of not leaving a successor to pay him funeral honors frightened him greatly and, for this reason, he went once again to the Sanctuary of Delphi, bringing about the fulfillment of the prophecy to which he was destined.

Freud, who also called himself an atheist and an enemy of the gods, is astonished by the way everything is organized, leading to situations caused by the end of time, in a more than perfect fit of nature. Laius decides to have a child, despite the curse that haunts and persecutes him mercilessly. He plots a ruse against fate and the gods; miraculously, the king of the neighboring country has a sterile marriage and desperately wants a child. Everything falls into place perfectly. Life goes on in an orderly fashion, until, accidentally, a drunkard who knew the truth about Oedipus' adoption stops him and tells him the story. He is outraged at having been deceived by this whole group of people and seeks help from an oracle who predicts a cruel sentence that will drive him mad, because he loved his parents and was a good man. In an attempt to escape his fateful fate and shame, he runs away, only to come across the adventurer who had prostrated himself at the entrance to Thebes and, having been educated to be king in his city, succeeding his adoptive father, King Polybus, he deciphers the riddle that had been set to him by the monster. Solving the challenge would grant him the status of King and the right to marry the widow of the previous priest. Thus, there is a succession of apparently random events that lead the young Oedipus to serve his sentence, under the most absolute and cunning silence.

If Oedipus were not an impetuous man and if, by chance, he sought out his parents to talk, there is a possibility that the story would be different, since King Polybus was not his biological father, there was no risk whatsoever that he would become his executioner. There was no way for him to foresee any movement of destiny, because the oracular message needed interpretation and, in his case, when the Oracle revealed his fate, it was talking about the inexorability of Destiny and not about who, exactly, would be his victim of parricide.

So how can any kind of crime be attributed to Oedipus? His ignorance led him to an apparently normal existence, which is why Sophocles says that the best existence is one that goes through life in the absence of wisdom. As much as he was guilty of his actions, everything was plotted before he was born and, as much as he tried to escape the inevitable, he could not, precisely because he was ignorant of what he should, in fact, avoid. A blind man running in any direction, fleeing from something unknown.

For Corrêa Netto (1987, p. 78-80) “Oedipus is the author of seven crimes and not two as Freud points out. He is a parricide and an agent of incest; we can add that he is a regicide, since Laius was king of Thebes. Oedipus defies destiny: the oracle of Delphi had predicted his parricide. There is no way to escape the voice and command of the gods, in this case Pythian Apollo. He could never escape his destiny; in other words, he had no right to be welcomed in Corinth. Oedipus then commits a fourth crime: he defies destiny, the oracles, the divine will. He is a pagan heretic. He had no right to exist, to come into the world, repudiated in advance by his father, perhaps the first filicide in the history of Psychoanalysis; stubborn, he was born... Male or female, we already have Oedipus the author of five crimes. He is now faced with the sixth crime. His condition, however, the human condition itself, is marked by yet another contradiction: challenged by the Sphinx, he must overcome her by showing his knowledge; but isn't that like eating from the Tree of Evil? Epistemophilia is also a crime, and it is no coincidence that the proposed enigma deals precisely with human evolution, or, if we prefer, with human knowledge and understanding about existence. Oedipus is once again a criminal; he threatened the gods, he intended to illuminate the secret, the hidden, to solve mysteries, to shed light. This is one of the most dangerous paths; in every corner of the world or the mind, there is hidden what perhaps should not be revealed; for the crawling child, for the frightened client on the couch, for Oedipus, a pilgrim in his own land, to discover is to challenge, there is no escape: either impulse or the law. Finally, the seventh crime of our Theban brother: aggression. Surprised on his return journey by Laius' entourage, there is a conflict --- he wounds and kills. Now he will have to pay for his seventh crime, by the Law of Talion. Ahead of him

is Thebes, further on Colonus: the punishment will be terrible, and the punishment is his existence.”

The crimes that Corrêa Netto attributes to Oedipus are the same that any mortal human being commits throughout his life, being punished in an extraordinary way for his transgressions and yet he continues to do so, because human nature is, in its essence, marked by ignorance and the common man ignores that his audacity to learn constitutes an offense against the gods, a fact already reported in the book of Genesis, which culminates in the expulsion of Adam and Eve from the Garden, for having opened their eyes to the things of the world, that is, for having acquired knowledge. Gnosis is a necessary and inevitable evil and, as much as mechanisms can be created to punish men, this is soon forgotten by those who come after him, since the world depends on such actions to continue its march towards progress.

What prevents a man from loving his mother is the law that overrides the impulse and that, even though there is a tradition that prevents this, it continues to be sanctioned at all times and to cause horror in enlightened individuals with normal mental faculties and, among the most primitive peoples who do not have written laws, the sanctity of the maternal figure is exalted, transformed into a *taboo object*, not by chance.

Oedipus, blinded by the search for truth and justice for his people who suffer from the plagues that have befallen the Polis, spares no effort in unraveling the entire enigma that makes him its epicenter. With each step he takes towards the final solution, the plot becomes more complicated, contrary to what is presented in the interpretation of thinkers, because he, despite everything, is innocent; the entire framework of his existence was kept silent and even the reason why he was conceived is not explained to him, leaving him with the impression that it was nothing more than an accident that his parents took care to correct after his birth.

He would never believe in coincidences; but by this time, both his parents had already passed away and, to make matters worse, his biological mother had also passed away, leaving him in a sea of uncertainty and insecurity, wandering through a life he could not interpret, even though he was a priest of great wisdom, known as the one who defeated the terrible Sphinx that was strangling the youth of Thebes. Paradoxically, the individual who has overcome ignorance is not capable of interpreting his own existence and understanding the gods' plan for men.

The Oedipus complex does not only refer to boys; with regard to girls, Freud outlines a different evolutionary model for female sexuality. According to him, with the advent of the phallic phase, the girl also experiences the phallic/castrated relationship. While knowledge of the vagina is non-existent for the younger child, clitoral eroticization will lead the girl, at this stage, to fantasize about possessing a penis; often sublimating this through playing with dolls.

Sigmund argues that the clitoris is configured as a tiny penis that would tend to grow and become the same as that of boys. The emphasis on phallic valorization would be similar for girls and boys. The anatomical misinterpretation, by the girl associating clitoris/penis, would maintain in the girl the fantasy of being phallic, that is, the fantasy of also possessing the *phallus* or penis. Even with the initial perception of female castration, children still have the fantasy that the women they love are phallic. Only the others are castrated. Female sexuality is, therefore, at this moment, phallic. The clitoris is a phallic correlate. The desire for it to grow is progressively frustrated by the perception of reality and the girl discovers that she is castrated. As a result, she does not yet discover her femininity, but magically sets out to conquer the valued organ. Within the family group, the father is the phallic representative. The girl then directs her affections towards her father. It is not the father who is directly sought, but possession of the penis, which represents strength and power. In this search, the bond between the father and the mother becomes clear to him. It is the mother who attracts him with her femininity. The girl then begins to imitate her, internalizing the maternal feminine values, and with them becoming attractive to the father. Thus, as the fear of castration becomes non-existent, the identification mechanism begins as a form of defense. Feminine values are progressively acquired within the process of conquering the father, sublimating the guilt for her incestuous desire for a forbidden object.

Carl Gustav Jung (1875-1961), a disciple and dissident of Sigmund, called the girl's Oedipus phase the *Electra Complex*, based on the interpretation of the key character's behavior in encouraging Orestes to avenge his father by murdering his mother, Clytemnestra. However, in Greek mythology, this character does not represent as well as Oedipus the erotic feeling and hatred towards the father and mother, respectively, when referring to both sexes. Possibly for this reason, the scientific community ended up abandoning the concept of the *Electra Complex* and adopting, for the occurrence of the phenomenon in both sexes, the concept of *the Oedipus Complex*.

In his self-analysis, Freud discovered that he was jealous of his young mother, Amalia, with her half-brother Philippe, the son of Jacob Freud with his first wife. In his unconscious delirium, he even thought that he was the son of the latter. This was the first step towards the discovery of the Oedipus Complex in his patients suffering from nervous disorders. Sigmund had had a troubled relationship with his father, who called him weak and cowardly, and he assumed that it was for this reason that he had a closer and more affectionate bond with his mother. This was a complex situation, because little Sigismund (Freud's original name), whom Amalia always called Sigi, was the apple of her eye, her most beloved and adored son; so much

so that she forbade her daughters from playing the piano while Sigi was studying, because it bothered him. As for his father, he had kept Freud's foreskin in a Jewish Bible, with the inscription of the date on which the circumcision had taken place. All this shows that there was a conflict between father and son, each fighting for possession of the object of their love, and Amália represented, in this confusion, the *bone of discord*. To achieve this, Freud only had to enter his own dark world and explore his relationships with his father and mother for him to have before him the enlightenment he needed to create his theory and explore the psychic world of his patients.

CONCLUSION

The Oedipus Complex is characterized as one of the most complex constructions of human existence and its discovery and systematization by the Master of Vienna represents one of the greatest scientific contributions of Psychoanalysis to all fields of human knowledge. In the field of education, it has helped pedagogues and educators to conduct their work with greater security and balance, especially when intervention in the psychic fields is required.

It is an unconscious phase for the child, which they go through without major complications if the family, educators and other people involved treat the occurrence of the phenomenon with due responsibility and commitment to their psychosexual development, not pretending that nothing is happening or treating it with astonishment. The right amount of understanding and emotional support is the best way to have a healthy and full affective-sexual life in adulthood. In this sense, psychoanalytic theories have helped a great deal.

Freud advances on a complex and difficult terrain to solve, because the universality of the Oedipus Complex does not mean that everyone treats it with the same deference and respect that was and is required by Freudian psychoanalysis, which considers it an extremely important stage in the formation of the human personality. In this sense, Sigmund never studied it in isolation from the entire psychological set of the being and in the various cases in which he worked as a clinician and therapist, when reporting them, he made it very clear how the appropriate treatment given to the child, at this stage, can help him not to go down the path of neurosis as a way of compensating for his deficient ego formation.

Anthropological studies carried out among peoples where the father figure is not central to the family structure show that the Oedipus complex continues to exist, proving its universality; however, the form of manifestation is different from that developed by Freud, having as a model the traditional Viennese bourgeois family of the late 19th and early 20th

centuries. What has been found, with greater transparency, is that the aforementioned process of love and hate, by children and even by adults, occurs towards and from the existence of an object of power, not necessarily that it has to be a male figure, as its existence and occurrence has demonstrated in matricentric and matriarchal societies, and even where the figure of the human father has been transmuted into some totemic representation in the form of an animal.

Sigmund, throughout his scientific life, presented several hypotheses and theories that could, in some way, clarify the occurrence of the Oedipus Complex phenomenon. It is not appropriate to explain them here, for various reasons; however, there is one in particular that deserves mention. According to him, man evolved from a specimen that reached adulthood at the age of five and, as the complex occurs around the age of three and a half, this may mean gonadotropic maturation, culminating in the desire for genetic cathexis discharge. He continues arguing that in the evolutionary process, man gained an extra life, with his existence extended *ad infinitum*, in what can be interpreted by the unconscious, arriving at the current model of psychosexual development.

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